

RESEARCH HISTORY OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE FIELD

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Abstract. *This article explores the research history of the English Language field, the reasons why it has changed over the years to come to its current level. We will also cite a number of useful information in the study of the history of the study of this language. By unraveling this historical tapestry, the article aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the evolution of English studies and its future trajectories.*

Key words: *English, American accent, field of study, global literature, cultural studies, technology, language pattern, evolution, literary realm, exploration.*

ИСТОРИЯ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ В ОБЛАСТИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *В данной статье исследуется история исследования области английского языка, причины, по которым она менялась с годами, чтобы прийти к современному уровню. Также мы приведем ряд полезных сведений при изучении истории изучения этого языка. язык. Распутывая эту историческую картину, статья призвана обеспечить всестороннее понимание эволюции изучения английского языка и его будущих траекторий.*

Ключевые слова: *английский язык, американский акцент, область исследования, мировая литература, культурологические исследования, технологии, языковая модель, эволюция, литературная сфера, исследование.*

Introduction

English is a West Germanic language spoken in England. Current English is currently the most widely spoken language in the world. History of the English language takes many things to many and continents. There are several English languages countries, Great Britain, USA, Canada, Australia, Ireland. It is the first language of most people in New Zealand. Mandarin in this world it is the most widely spoken mother tongue after Chinese and Spanish. English language is the most popular language as a language. English speaking people in general the number of people who speak the mother tongue and speak other languages exceeds the number. English is the

language of the European Union, many Commonwealth countries and The United Nations is the official language of many world organizations language.

Literature analysis and methodology

History of the English language in the Anglo-Saxon kingdoms of England and now South-east Scotland, but later control of the Kingdom of Northumbria started under. It was in this region that English appeared. The history of the English language in America has three and a half centuries. It is characterized by the creation of the first period (from the beginning of the 17th century to the end of the 18th century) and late (XIX-XX centuries), characterized by the formation of American dialects of the English language. At the beginning of the early period, English in America generally coincided with the standards adopted in England in the 17th century. The English pronunciation of the 16th and 17th centuries is significantly different from the pronunciation of the modern language. The changes did not affect English in America or at all, or had less impact on it. So, by the end of the period we are considering, significant deviations from the Fraternal standards of literary pronunciation have already been identified in America. The most important discrepancies are related to the completion of the English Dictionary in America. Due to the appropriation of words in many other languages throughout history, modern there is a very large vocabulary in English. Not only other Europe in modern English from languages, but from all continents, including Hindi and African mastered at. The history of the English language is such a history of the emergence of the English language as well eventful. On the territory of modern Great Britain lived different peoples, it is one how many times were captured and released, and each invasion was for Great Britain wanted to "invent" a new language. This is manifested in the variety of the English language.

Discussion

The differences between English in America (AE) and English in Britain (BE) have been discussed for a long time. The debate about whether AE should be considered an independent language, finally separated from BE, continues in our time. The period of formation of the English-speaking community in North America in the XVII-XVIII centuries is characteristic of the linguistic situation. By this time, in England itself, the National Literary norm had already been formed, which, in addition to dialects, served as a communication system. An important factor contributing to the expansion of the social base of literary English in America was the high prestige of education and a certain conservatism of the American educational system, which for a long time followed British standards. A.D. according to Schweitzer has every reason to assume that the degree of variability in the structure of a literary language at one level or another is associated with

its model of formation. As an example, the author addresses the history of the formation of literary English in England and the United States. The formation of the National Literary norm in England took place around the only center – London, the language of which had a decisive influence on the processes of formation and stabilization of the national language norm. Such a model of the literary norm is A.D. Schweitzer calls it monocentric. In North America, the situation was different, where, as noted above, at a very early stage, the standard of literary norm continued to be the London language, viz. an extrasentric model that works with a center outside a given range. Then another model was put on this model, which was associated with the formation of such centers in colonial America as Boston, New York, Philadelphia, Richmond, where the formation of the literary norm continues rapidly. The author defines this model as polycentric. This polysentrism of the American variant manifested itself in different ways at different levels of the linguistic structure, significantly affecting the phonetic level. The fact that standard American English was formed under the influence of complex and contrasting factors in the conditions of high geographical and social mobility of the population, with an emphasis on both the norm of the English version and the regional norms of the colonial centers . the most common version left a certain mark on its condition and structure. Its distinguishing features are the uncertainty of the boundaries and the significant variability of the turbidity and structure.

Result

Through this given information, we have examined the research history and origins of the English Language field. As a result, we observed the evolution of the English language and how much it was in ancient times.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the research history of the English language unfolds as a captivating narrative, evolving through centuries of linguistic inquiry, literary exploration, and cultural introspection. This journey not only celebrates the richness of the English language but also anticipates the exciting avenues that future research endeavors may unveil.

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